

Characterization of Thermal Stability of Al₂TiO₅-Based Functional Graded Ceramics

Thinzar Wut Yee^{*}, Zeya Oo^{**}, R Sokkalangam^{***}, P Vasant^{***}

Corresponding author: auwe1006@gmail.com

Abstract

This research paper focused on the diffraction study of thermal stability in functionally-graded aluminium titanate Al₂TiO₅- based functional graded ceramic composites. The main aims of the research were to study the parameters that control the thermal stability of Al₂TiO₅- based functional graded ceramics and to evaluate the effect of atmospheres, in the range of 20-1400°C. A high-temperature vacuum annealing process was proposed for the design of functionally graded Al₂TiO₅- ceramics. The effect of the atmospheres (air, argon and 50 % oxygen, 50% argon) on the isothermal stability of Al₂TiO₅ at 1100°C and its decomposition behavior in the temperature range of 20–1400°C were characterized by ND. There was no decomposition of Al₂TiO₅ in air and argon, as well as oxygen partial pressure of up to 1100°C, but it occurred between 1150 and 1300°C.

1. Introduction

Amongst the oxide ceramics, alumina (Al₂O₃) is a commonly used ceramic which has an enormous range of technological and industrial applications due to its properties such as high thermal conductivity, high hardness, and resistance to many corrosive media, abrasion resistance, low density, and high electrical resistivity. In addition, due to its strong demand in diverse applications, alumina is frequently incorporated with other materials to obtain more advanced or specific properties and microstructures.

In 1980, Functionally-Graded Materials (FGMs) were introduced as multi-functional materials which contain various compositions for specific applications [1]. To achieve the highest possible mechanical properties of FGMs, tailored designs of functionally-graded Al₂TiO₅-Al₂O₃ were developed [2, 3, 4]. Aluminum titanate (Al₂TiO₅), is widely used as a refractory material and as a thermal insulator in engine components by virtue of its low thermal expansion coefficient ($1 \times 10^{-6} \text{C}^{-1}$), high melting point (1860°C), low thermal conductivity, and excellent thermal shock resistance [5, 6]. However, the full potential of Al₂TiO₅ has been limited by its low fracture toughness, low mechanical strength and poor high-temperature stability.

Recent developments in layered ceramics have provided a strategy for designing laminates with increased strength and toughness. These structures have an outermost homogeneous layer to provide strength or wear resistance, and an underlying heterogeneous layer to provide toughness [7]. Unlike more traditional layered structures which promote toughness by interlayer crack deflection or strength by incorporating macroscopic compressive residual stresses, the new approach deliberately seeks to produce strong interlayer bonding to eliminate residual macroscopic stresses. Al₂TiO₅-based Functional Graded Ceramics has been

^{*} Demonstrator, Department of Physics, Bago University, Myanmar

^{**} Visiting Professor, Department of Engineering Physics, Yangon Technological University, Myanmar

^{***} Department of Fundamental Science and Mathematics, University Technology Petronas, Malaysia

^{***} Department of Fundamental Science and Mathematics, University Technology Petronas, Malaysia

used in many industrial fields, such as corrosion resistant coating, anti-oxidation coating and thermal barrier coating under high temperature, refractory materials and structural materials in metallurgical industries [8]. In this paper, characterisation of thermal stability of Al_2TiO_5 -based Functional Graded Ceramics will be discussed by using Rietveld Diffraction Analysis method [9].

1.1. General Objectives

The main objectives were studying the parameters (such as, atmosphere, temperature changing, grain sizes and temperature constant) that control the thermal stability in functional-graded material: aluminium titanate (Al_2TiO_5 -based ceramics).

The specific objectives were:

- to synthesize functionally-graded Al_2TiO_5 - based systems by using a new modification approach: die-pressing followed by vacuum heat treatment.
- to study the parameters that control the thermal stability of functionally-graded Al_2TiO_5 systems produced by vacuum heat treatment.
- to analyze the characteristics of functionally-graded Al_2TiO_5 - based developments by neutron diffraction (ND), scanning electron microscopy (SEM).
- to conduct diffraction studies on the thermal stability of Al_2TiO_5 - Al_2O_3 composites.

2. Experimental Procedures

In order to achieve the objectives, this research specified two major aspects of interactive materials processing and characterisation.

2.1. Processing of Al_2TiO_5 - based systems

The raw materials used in the synthesis of Al_2TiO_5 -based ceramics consisted of high purity commercial powders of Al_2O_3 (99.9%) and TiO_2 (99.5%). These dry powders were mixed in the ratio of 1:1 by mortar and pestle. Ethanol was added during mixing to produce a slurry which was then dried in a ventilated oven at 100°C for 24h. Cylindrical bars of length 20 mm and diameter 12 mm were then fabricated and pressed by steel die at 150 MPa, followed by sintering at 1500°C in air for 2 h.

2.2. Characterisation of Al_2TiO_5 - based systems

The characterisation of thermal stability of Al_2TiO_5 -based ceramics in different atmospheres and temperatures was analyzed by ND, SEM. The reformations of phase composition of Al_2TiO_5 - based ceramics were analyzed by ND. All data analysis were utilised by Rietveld Diffraction Analysis [9]. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the research methodology for Al_2TiO_5 -based ceramics.

Fig 1. Flow chart of research methodology of Al_2TiO_5 -based ceramics.

2.3. Neutron Diffraction (ND)

Neutrons are useful for research purposes as they have a wavelength approximately equal to the spacing between atoms in molecules; they are therefore able to produce interference patterns from the atomic lattice. However, neutrons are electrically neutral and are thus capable of passing through the atomic electron cloud unhindered and straight to the nucleus. This ability gives researchers the opportunity to obtain unique information about many elements. Neutrons also have magnetic moments, so they can probe magnetic materials

to reveal magnetic structure. They also have energy similar to the vibration energy of atoms in solids and liquids, thus endowing them with the ability to view the motions of atoms in molecules in detail.

Neutrons are useful for probing solids and liquids. It is one of the many tools that researchers utilize to view atomic structures, with the other tools being light, electrons and X-rays. One of the tools used for neutrons diffraction is the diffractometer, an apparatus designed to determine angles at which diffraction occurs for powdered specimens such as ceramics. The diffractometer utilized in this project was the Medium-Resolution Powder Diffractometer (MRPD) at ANSTO's High Flux Australian Reactor (HIFAR), where the neutrons were produced via the fission process and Polaris Medium – Solution, High – Intensity Powder Diffractometer, United Kingdom01, pulsed spallation neutron source ISIS, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory [10].

The ND data collection was performed using a medium resolution powder diffractometer (MRPD) located at the Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation in Lucas Heights, NSW. The operation conditions were $\lambda = 1.667 \text{ \AA}$, 2θ range = $4 - 138^\circ$, step size = 0.1° , counting time $\sim 40\text{-}50 \text{ s/step}$, monochromator of 8 Ge crystals (115 reflection), and 32 ^3He detectors 4° apart. The relative phase abundances of TiO_2 (rutile), Al_2TiO_5 and Al_2O_3 and the models of TiO_2 , Al_2TiO_5 and Al_2O_3 were performed for the Rietveld analysis (See Table 1).

2.3.1. Rietveld Diffraction Analysis

Rietveld diffraction analysis is especially used for the least-squares refinement program which has been written in Algol 60 to be run on an Electrologica X-8 computer having 48 K words (26bits) core storage and magnetic tape units [11]. Today, the necessity of comparing graphical data in the form of calculated and observed diffraction patterns were interested. In addition, instead of using the usual integrated intensities, extensive use is being made of an automatic incremental plotter.

The value of Rietveld method [11] for the analysis of X-ray diffraction and neutron diffraction patterns is now well established. This is a method for crystal structure refinement that involves the fitting of a complete experimental diffraction pattern with calculated profiles and background. The first computer program for the implementation of the Rietveld method [12] was described by Young [13]. This program was written specifically for the data analysis of neutron diffraction data from the fixed wavelength diffractometers. The program had two steps in its operation: a data preparation and a refinement step. The results of two Rietveld refinement round robins organized by the Commission on Powder Diffraction (CPD) of the International Union of Crystallography were published by Hill [14]. These studies were designed to evaluate a cross section of the currently used Rietveld software, to examine the effect of different refinement strategies, to access the accuracy and precision of the parameters obtained in a Rietveld refinement, and to compare different instruments and methods of data collection.

The Rietveld analysis method uses crystal structure and diffraction peaks profile to generate x-ray or neutron diffraction patterns via a process of least square refinement which minimizes the differences between the observed and the calculated patterns.

Rietica-LHPM Microsoft Windows 95 program [15] which derives from the Hill-Howard-Hunter LHPM program [9]. Crystal structure data including atom coordinates and unit cell parameters were taken from the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) (see Table 3.2). The computations involved adjustment of the specimen displacement, phase scale factors,

zero adjustment, polynomial fit parameters for the pattern-background, refinable lattice parameters, individual atom thermal parameters, overall thermal parameters, instrumentation parameters such as U, V, W, asymmetry parameter AS and 2θ – scale offset and peak profile functions (pseudo-Voigt with asymmetry).

Refinement trails of two types were conducted – the first with random orientation (RO) assumed for all phases, and second with the correcting the intensities I_k of Bragg peaks for preferred orientation (PO) using the preferred correction [16].

$$P_k = (r^2 \cos^2 \alpha_k + r^{-1} \sin^2 \alpha_k)^{-3/2} \quad (1)$$

where r is the refinable preferred orientation (PO) parameters.

Pattern-background polynomial parameters were used to fit the background of data collections. Polynomial coefficient B_0 , B_1 , B_2 and B_3 and diffraction angle 2θ is related as follow:

$$y_{bi} = B_0 + B_1(2\theta_i) + B_2(2\theta_i)^2 + B_3(2\theta_i)^3 \quad (2)$$

B_0 , B_1 , B_2 , and B_3 was satisfactory for the pattern background refinement, but sometimes higher orders B_4 and B_5 were needed because depending on data behavior collection from XRD, ND and SRD.

Refinement strategies on Rietveld phase composition were determined in powder mixtures using the “ZMV” expressions [16].

Relative phase compositions:

$$W_k = \frac{S_k (ZMV)_k}{\sum_i S_i (ZMV)_i} \quad (3)$$

where W_k is the weight fraction of phase k , S_k is the Rietveld phase scale factor, Z is the number of formula per unit cell, M is the mass of formula weight and V is the unit cell volumes. The estimated standards deviations (esds) parameter, σ_j was performed.

The figures-of-merit or R-values after refining, Bragg R, profile R_p , weighted profile R_{wp} , expected R_{exp} factors formulae are utilised to find the goodness of fitting (GOF) by using equation (4).

The goodness of fitting (GOF) is determined by the following equation.

$$GOF = \left(\frac{R_{wp}}{R_{exp}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Where R_{exp} and R_{wp} are called expected profile and weight profile factors respectively. Equation (4) is the last statement of the Rietveld analysis because the best value of GOF should be 1.0. However, some researchers have suggested that value should be less than four for phase abundance data analysis [17]. The difference plots between the observation and the calculation patterns play an important role for assessing the determination good refinement. The two patterns should give a flat difference for a well-refined model. The difference plots may show indication of the presence of undetected phases or inaccuracies in the background or peak shape modelling.

In the analysis, the refinement parameters were polynomial background correction, diffractometer zero correction, phase scale factors for each phase, atom parameters, such as atom coordinates, lattice parameters, and individual thermal parameters and over all thermal

parameters and the instrumental parameters. For the Rietveld data analysis, list of structure of phase models, authors' name are described in Table 1.

Table 1. List of structure models, International Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) number and authors' name for the Rietveld analysis

Structural models	ICSD number	Authors
alpha-Al ₂ O ₃ (Corundum)	73725	Maslen et al., (1993) [18]
Al ₂ TiO ₅ (Aluminium Titanate)	71356	Epicier et al., (1991) [19]
TiO ₂ (Rutile)	64987	Shintani et al., (1975) [20]

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of Atmospheres on the Thermal Stability of Aluminium Titanate

The neutron diffraction data were analysed by Rietveld analysis. The model of Epicier et al., (1991) [19] for Al₂TiO₅ gave the most suitable and acceptable refinement results. The refinements parameters were the background profile parameters (B's), 2 θ -zero, scale factor (s), profile broadening parameters (U,V,W), lattice parameters (a,b,c), preferred orientation factor (PO), asymmetry factor (As), mixing parameter (Υ) and atom isotropic thermal parameters (T). The atom coordinates (x,y,z) were not refined.

The relative phase abundances for the composition of isothermal stability Al₂TiO₅ samples were performed by the Rietveld analysis method [12]. Fig. 2 shows the neutron diffraction difference plots for Al₂TiO₅ in air at temperature 1100°C after Rietveld analysis. The observed data were shown by a (+) sign, and the calculated data by a solid line (red). Vertical blue bars represent the Bragg peak positions for Al₂O₃, Al₂TiO₅, and TiO₂ from the top to the bottom respectively. The difference plot between observation and calculation was shown by green line. Wavelength for ND is 1.665Å.

Fig 2. ND (MRPD) Rietveld difference plots for coarse grain size Al₂TiO₅ in air at 1100°C.

Fig 3. Isothermal stability of Al₂TiO₅ at 1100°C in air. Error bars indicate two estimated standard deviation $\pm 2 \sigma$. Legend: Al₂TiO₅ (■), Al₂O₃ (◆), TiO₂ (Δ)

Fig 4. Isothermal stability of Al₂TiO₅ at 1100°C in argon atmosphere. Error bars indicate two estimated standard deviation $\pm 2 \sigma$. Legend: Al₂TiO₅ (■), Al₂O₃ (◆), TiO₂ (Δ)

Fig 5. Isothermal stability of Al₂TiO₅-based ceramic at 1100°C in the atmosphere of 50% of oxygen and 50% argon. Error bars indicate two estimated standard deviation $\pm 2 \sigma$. Legend: Al (■), Al₂O₃ (◆), TiO₂ (Δ) [1]

Fig 6. SEM micrographs of isothermal stability Al₂TiO₅ decomposed in the atmosphere of 50% of oxygen and 50% of argon [1]

A comparative study on the thermal stability of Al₂TiO₅- based ceramics at constant temperature 1000 °C in air and argon are investigated. In addition, the influence of oxygen partial pressures on the range and on-set temperature of thermal stability in Al₂TiO₅-based ceramics are performed (Figure 3, 4 and Figure 5). First of all, the thermal stability of Al₂TiO₅ -based ceramics in the difference atmosphere (air and argon) at temperature 1100°C has found dependent on ageing environment. Results show that, while Al₂TiO₅ is relatively stable up to 6 h during isothermal ageing at 1100°C in air, it suffers an accelerated decomposition in argon

because the decomposition rate of Al_2TiO_5 -based at 1100°C is significantly enhanced in argon where $> 80\%$ of Al_2TiO_5 decomposed after 4 h soaking when compared to less than 10% in atmospheric air. When the ageing atmosphere was changed to 50% argon and 50% oxygen, the decomposition rate was considerably reduced compared with the rate for 100% argon but more substantial than the rate for air. A closer look at the results in Fig 3-5 suggests that the rate of phase decomposition of Al_2TiO_5 is dependent on the atmosphere or oxygen partial pressure during isothermal ageing. This implies that the oxygen partial pressure in the isothermal plays a key role in triggering the thermal instability via oxygen non-stoichiometry changes and/or disordering of cations in Al_2TiO_5 [21]. If the oxygen partial pressure is the main cause of thermal stability in different atmosphere, the decomposition rate of Al_2TiO_5 should depend on the variations of the oxygen partial pressure.

Scanning electronic micrographs of Al_2TiO_5 decomposed in atmosphere of 50% of oxygen and 50% of argon was shown in Figure 6. It shows more clearly Al_2TiO_5 (phase abundance 93.8 wt%), TiO_2 (phase abundance 2.58wt%) and Al_2O_3 (phase abundance 3.64wt%). This verifies that the decomposition process in atmosphere in air leading to a phase composition as indicated by neutron diffraction (ND).

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Prof Jim, Low, Department of Applied Physics and Imaging Physics, Faculty of Engineering and Science, Curtin University Australia for his fully supporting to come up this research work. Finally, this research was supported by U Nyi Hla Nge Foundation, Yangon, Myanmar for the financial supporting.

References

- Buscaglia V, Caracciolo F, Leoni M, Nanni P, Viviani M & Lematre J. (1997). *Synthesis, Sintering and Expansion of $\text{Al}_{0.8}\text{Mg}_{0.8}\text{Ti}_{1.6}\text{O}_5$: a Low-Thermal-Expansion Material Resistant to Thermal Decomposition*. Journal of Materials Science, 32, 6525-6531.
- Cleveland J J & Bradt R C. (1978). Grain Size Microcracking Relations for Pseudobrookite Oxides, Journal of the American Society, 61, 478-481.
- Epicer T, Thomas G, Wohlfromm H and Moya J S .(1991). *High Resolution Electron Microscopy Study of the Cationic Disorder in Al_2TiO_5* , Journal of Materials Research 6, 138-145.
- Hill R J and Howard C J. (1987). *Quantitative Phase Analysis from Neutron Powder Diffraction Data using the Rietveld Method*. Journal of Applied Crystallography, 20, 467- 474.
- Hill R J, Howard C J and Hunter B. A B. (1995). *Computer Program for Rietveld Analysis of Fixed Wavelength X-ray and Neutron Powder Diffraction Patterns*. Australian Atomic Energy Commission (now ANSTO) Report No. M112. Lucas Heights Research Laboratories, New South Wales, Australia
- Hunter B A & Howard C J. (1998). *A Computer Program for Rietveld Analysis of Fixed Wavelength X-Ray and Neutron Powder Diffraction Patterns*. Australian Atomic Energy Commission (now ANSTO) Report No. M112, Lucas Heights Research Laboratories, New South Wales, Australia.
- Hull S, Smith R I, David W, Hanon A, Mayers J & Cywinski R. (1992). *The Polaris Powder Diffractometer at ISIS*. Physica B, 180-181, 1000-1002.
- Kisi E H. (1994). *Rietveld Analysis of Powder Diffraction Patterns*. Materials Forum, 18, 135-153.
- Low I M. (1998). *a Processing of an In-Situ Layered and Graded Alumina-Aluminium Titana Composites*. Materials Research Bulletin, 33, 1475-1482.
- Low I. M, Lawrence D & Smith R I. (2005). *Factors Controlling the Thermal Stability of Aluminium Titanate in Vacuum, Journal of the American Ceramic Society*. 88, 2957-2961.

- Maslen E N, Streltsov V A Streltsova N R, **Ishizawa N and Satow Y. (1993). *Synchrotron X-Ray Study of the Electron Density in Alpha-Al₂O₃***. Acta Crystallographica, B49, 973-980.
- Oo. Z. (2013). Ph. D Thesis, ***Characterisation of Thermal Stability, Microstructures and Properties of Al₂TiO₅- and Ti₃SiC₂-based Ceramic***. Curtin University Australia.
- O'Connor B H & Li D Y. (2000). ***Influence of Refinement Strategies on Rietveld Phase Composition Determination***. Advances in X-Ray Analysis 42, 204-211.
- Pratapa. S. (1997). ***Synthesis and Characterization of Functionally-graded Aluminium Titanate/ZTA System Ceramics***. MSc Thesis, Curtin University of Technology, Perth, WA.
- Pratapa S & Low I M. (1998). ***Infiltration - Processed, Functionally Graded Aluminium Titanate/ Zirconia-Alumina Composite: I Microstructural Characterisation and Physical Properties***. Journal of Materials Science, 33, 3047-3053.
- Rietveld H M. (1969). ***A Profile Refinement Method for Nuclear and Magnetic Structures***. Journal of Applied Crystallography. 2, 65-71.
- Rietveld H M. (1967). ***Line Profiles of Neutron Powder-Diffraction Peaks for Structure Refinement***. Acta Crystallographica. 22, 151-152.
- Shintani H, Sato S and Saito Y. (1975). ***Electron-Density Distribution in Rutile Crystals***. Acta Crystallographica B24, 31, 1981-1982.
- Skala R D. (2000). ***Development of a Functionally-Graded Aluminium Titanate/Aluminium Titanate/Alumina Composite***. Ph. D Thesis, Curtin University of Technology, Perth, Australia.
- Xu G. Xu et al. Ceramics International 42 2016, 14107-14112.
- Young R A (Ed). (1993). ***The Rietveld Method. International Union of Crystallography***. Britain: Oxford University Press, Great Britain.